

Pod phenotypic variation in the Snap Bean Panel (SBP)

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Developed by the Plant Genetic Group of SERIDA

This graphic document shows the pod diversity included in the Snap Bean Panel (SBP).
For-five pods per line are showed on a 1 cm grid template.
The pods were collected from the 2020 field trial and completed from the 2021 field trial

Compiled by the Plant Genetic Group of SERIDA

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